

From Blade to BigQuery

The Aerosense Data Gateway – an open-source turbine-to-cloud data engineering example

Possible tags

- Open-source
- Octue
- Cloud
- Sensing
- Remote sensing
- Internet of things
- IOT
- Data

Leader

Getting data from wind turbines cleaned, sorted, and into the hands of engineers is a common but overwhelming task. Security, reliability, edge/cloud engineering particulars and the FAIR digitalisation principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) must all be considered, requiring a large investment of time and a rare combination of skills.

To help accelerate this process, a complete, production-tested example has been built and open-sourced for engineers to draw from. This is the [Aerosense Data Gateway](#), which gathers large quantities of data from the edge, then cleans, uploads, structures and stores it, allowing easy access and onward use. The code is freely available on GitHub to view, use, and copy.

The Gateway is an integral part of the [Aerosense project](#), which has developed the first ever MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical System) surface pressure and acoustic measurement system for wind turbine blades, including a system of digital twins that utilise that data.

The Gateway was built by [Octue](#), a software development consultancy specialising in renewables and climate. Octue's mission is to help scientists work more effectively with data. Using an Open-Source business model, Octue builds and maintains [a range of tools](#) to aid the wind industry in the path to digitalisation.

Body

The Aerosense Data Gateway comprises three main components:

- **An onboard application** that receives, parses, and uploads blade sensor data
- **A serverless Cloud Function** that tags and streams this data to Google BigQuery
- **A BigQuery database** for highly scalable long-term data storage and querying

These components are shown below in the figure.

Overview

The Gateway collects data from any number of sensor nodes, automatically uploads it to the cloud (or stores it locally for testing purposes), and enables visualisation and data analysis

anytime, anywhere. Sensor nodes can be controlled interactively or automatically using simple JSON-encoded routine files via an intuitive command line interface (CLI). To avoid data loss in the event of an internet outage, data sent to the cloud is backed up locally and upload is retried until successful if it initially fails. The Gateway is also resilient to power outages via daemonisation. The cloud function preprocesses the data and can dynamically scale up from nothing to handling limitless turbines. Security is provided through the use of Google Cloud Service accounts. Finally, the code is open-source, fully tested, and fully documented.

The onboard application

The Gateway is written in python and tested to run on any x86_64, armv7 or aarch64 processor architecture. For Aerosense's needs, a simple Raspberry Pi was used. High-bandwidth raw data is received from each sensor node via Bluetooth and buffered into a serial port. Two processes then work in parallel - the first continuously reads data from the serial port into a process-safe queue (this allows high-bandwidth data transfer while avoiding data loss stemming from the relatively small serial port buffer overflowing); the second continuously takes data from the queue, parses it, and streams it to the cloud. To control these processes and the sensor nodes, a simple and versatile CLI was developed to run remotely on the Raspberry Pi in the field, on wind researchers' laptops in the lab, and on the hardware team's computers while developing the sensor nodes. This eliminated any disparity between development, testing, and production uses of the Gateway.

Automated management of Gateway fleets

To efficiently and scalably monitor multiple wind turbines while ensuring the latest security patches and features are installed on all of them, the fleet of Gateways are managed via Balena, an internet-of-things (IOT) orchestrator that allows operating system and software updates to be automatically pushed in real time. Each Gateway and its hardware is also individually controllable and monitorable via the platform.

The serverless Cloud Function

A Google Cloud Function was set up to pre-process uploaded data and stream it to the BigQuery database. The beautiful thing about the cloud function is its dynamic scalability. When it's not in use, it costs nothing; when data is uploaded, it just "spins up", processes and sends it to BigQuery, and "spins down" again. And as more Gateways are installed on more turbines or the volume of incoming data increases, more instances of the cloud function can automatically spin up to handle it. This minimises costs, automates scaling, and prevents extreme cost spirals in the event of a malicious DDOS-like attack or other malfunction (sensible scale-up limits are set by default and can be increased or decreased as required). Another key purpose of the cloud function is to restrict the ability to write to the database to a well-controlled and secure environment rather than granting edge hardware direct write access. This keeps the database safe in the event that any edge hardware becomes compromised.

The BigQuery Database

A Google BigQuery database (usually referred to as a dataset) is a highly scalable, highly available cloud database capable of storing and querying petabytes of data. An instance was set up with a schema designed to store raw measurements in a versatile way, enabling new

sensors or data types to be added without frequent migrations and changes to the schema. Materialised views were added to restructure the raw data dynamically, enabling easy and intuitive querying using basic SQL, Pandas/Numpy, and dashboarding tools such as Plotly's Dash.

Obstacles and solutions

One obstacle encountered early on was serial port buffer overflow. This arose when high bandwidth sensors, such as microphones, were added to the sensor nodes. These sensors flooded the serial port with data which, if read continuously, was easily handled. However, when the Gateway was initially developed, reading and uploading took place in serial in the same process, meaning that each time data was uploaded, reading had to pause. This would cause the serial port buffer to immediately fill up and overflow, resulting in the loss of valuable data. To fix this, the Gateway was parallelised. The reader and the uploader were given their own processes, allowing the reader to continuously empty data from the serial port buffer into an in-memory queue while the uploader worked in parallel.

Inefficiencies and human error in release and documentation processes were also experienced. To avoid these and save time, various automated deployment tools were developed to [deduce and check semantic versions](#) (using [Conventional Commits](#)), produce release notes, and release the software. Best practices in Continuous Integration and Delivery were also implemented, including automated releases and cross-platform testing on Linux, MacOS, and Windows.

Conclusion

The Aerosense Data Gateway is a fully-tested, open-source, and production-tested example of how to get data from the edge into the cloud. It provides wind turbine blade data collection, cloud ingress, and data lake storage in a secure, scalable, cost-effective, and resilient way. Combined with the wider Aerosense project, it is a useful solution for manufacturers to optimise the design of large flexible rotors and for owner/operators to detect faults and optimise their operations. The Gateway liberates wind energy scientists of a significant amount of software engineering and DevOps tedium so they can focus on what they do best – science.

Further reading

- The open-source code and documentation: github.com/aerosense-ai/data-gateway
- The Aerosense project: www.aerosense.ai
- Octue's open-source repositories: github.com/octue
- Octue's open-source tools: octue.com/tools

Biography

Marcus Lugg is a Senior Software Engineer at Octue. He has architected and developed several Open-Source Software (OSS) libraries and applications to aid wind energy researchers in working with data and data services. Marcus has an MPhys in Physics and, prior to working at Octue, helped develop textual classification systems using machine learning.

Affiliation

- Company name: Octue
- Author: Marcus Lugg MPhys, Senior Software Engineer
- Email: marcus@octue.com
- Address: Octue @ Aurora, British Antarctic Survey, High Cross, Madingley Road, Cambridge, Cambridgeshire, CB3 0ET
- Website: octue.com